

Physalolactone : A New Withanolide from *Physalis peruviana*

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Physalolactone, a new withanolide isolated from the leaves of *Physalis peruviana*, has been characterised as (17*S*, 20*S*, 22*R*)-6 α -chloro-4 β ,5 β ,14 α ,17,20-pentahydroxy-1-oxowitha-2,24-dienolide (I) from chemical and spectral evidences.

PHYSALIS peruviana Linn. (Solanaceae) is widely cultivated in India for its edible berries. We already¹ reported the structure determination of physoperuvine, a biogenetic variant of tropane alkaloids, isolated from its roots. The present paper describes the structure elucidation of a new withanolide, physalolactone(I), isolated from the leaves of the same plant.

Chromatographic resolution of the ether-soluble fraction of the alcoholic extract of the leaves of *P. peruviana* led to the isolation of a number of steroidal constituents, the major one of which was designated as physalolactone, C₂₉H₄₉O₈Cl. H₂O, m.p. 227-28°, [α]_D+29.4° (pyridine). It was recognised to have a 20-hydroxy-1-oxowitha-2,24-dienolide skeleton from spectral data discussed in the sequel.

Mass spectrum of physalolactone, in addition to the twin molecular ion peaks at m/e 538/540, showed important ion peaks at m/e 125 (65%), 152 (base peak)

and 169 (50%) due to ions *a*, *b* and *c* respectively. While the ions *a* and *b* are considered to be diagnostic peaks for a withanolide skeleton², ion *c* suggested the presence of a hydroxyl group at C-20.

The IR spectrum of physalolactone showed only one broad carbonyl absorption at 1673 cm⁻¹ (overlap of both α , β -unsaturated ketone and lactone³) and its UV spectrum showed maximum absorption at 217 nm (ϵ , 11,700), characteristic of the summation spectrum of enone and α , β -unsaturated lactone chromophores^{4,5}.

The PMR spectrum of physalolactone showed five methyl singlets, three of which are attributable to tertiary and two to vinylic methyls (Table 1). The low-field methyl singlet at δ , 1.24 for 21-methyl confirms the presence of a hydroxyl group at C-20, as indicated from mass spectrum. The olefinic protons at C-2 and C-3 appeared as doublet and double doublet, respectively at δ , 5.82 and 6.63.

TABLE 1—PMR DATA FOR PHYSALOLACTONE AND DERIVATIVES

Compd.	2-H	3-H	4-H	6-H	22-H	Me groups					
						19-H	18-H	21-H	27	&	28-H
I	5.82 <i>d</i> (10)	6.63 <i>dd</i> (10,2.5)	4.55 <i>m</i>	4.55 <i>m</i>	4.55 <i>m</i>	1.10 <i>s</i>	0.94 <i>s</i>	1.24 <i>s</i>	1.73	&	1.87 <i>s</i>
III	6.57 <i>d</i> (10)	6.70 <i>d</i> (10)	—	4.45 <i>m</i>	4.45 <i>m</i>	1.18 <i>s</i>	0.94 <i>s</i>	1.23 <i>s</i>	1.73	&	1.87 <i>s</i>
V	6.61 <i>d</i> (10)	6.74 <i>d</i> (10)	—	4.37 <i>dd</i> (10,4)	—	1.18 <i>s</i>	0.82 <i>s</i>	—	—	—	—
VI*	6.37 <i>d</i> (10)	6.86 <i>d</i> (10)	—	4.33 <i>dd</i> (10,5)	—	1.09 <i>s</i>	1.44 <i>s</i>	—	—	—	—

Spectra were recorded in 90 MHz in DMSO-*d*₆ soln. Chemical shifts are in δ units. Coupling constants (in Hz) are in parentheses. * in CDCl₃ soln.

The enone and lactone systems account for three of the eight oxygen atoms present in physalolactone molecule while the five hydroxyl functions, the presence of which was evident from five exchangeable proton signals in the PMR spectrum of the compound and from an ion peak at *m/e* 412 [M-(5H₂O+HCl)] in its mass spectrum accounted for the remaining five. Acetylation (Ac₂O-Et₃N) of physalolactone gave a monoacetate (II) and MnO₂ oxidation gave a pale yellow crystalline enedione (III), characterised by its UV absorption⁶ [λ_{max} 227 nm] and appearance of C-2 and C-3 protons as clean AB quartet centered around δ 6.63. The experiment indicates the presence of a secondary hydroxyl group at C-4. Jones oxidation of physalolactone afforded a mixture of a solid and a liquid ketone which were separated by chromatography. The liquid ketone (IV) gave a crystalline DNP derivative, characterised by its PMR spectrum which showed the presence of three vinylic methyl and a twelve line pattern for an ABX system besides the aromatic proton signals. The solid ketone (V) analysed for C₁₉H₂₂O₅Cl (M⁺, 366/368) and exhibited UV absorption maximum at 227 nm (ϵ , 8,700) attributable to an enedione chromophore⁶ and IR bands in the carbonyl region at 1750 (cyclopentanone), 1670 (enone) and 1716 cm⁻¹. The PMR spectrum of this ketone showed the presence of two tertiary methyls, two olefinic protons and two protons exchangeable with D₂O. The hydroxyl groups present in the ketone must be tertiary in nature as these are not amenable to oxidation and, therefore, the one-proton doublet at δ , 4.37 discernible in its PMR spectrum is due to a methine bound to the chlorine atom. Of the four available sites for tertiary hydroxyls in V, C-5 and C-14 appeared to be the preferred sites for these groups as no withanolide has yet been reported with oxygen functions at 8 or 9 position. Dehydration of solid ketone with KHSO₄-Ac₂O at 140° afforded a compound (VI) which in its PMR spectrum showed, in addition to expected signals, a methyl singlet at δ , 2.09 for an acetoxy grouping, an extra olefinic proton at δ , 5.68 and a low-field methylene proton signal at δ , 2.91 the chemical shift of which is attributable to C-16

methylene flanked between a carbonyl group and a double bond⁷. The tertiary acetoxy group must, therefore, be at C-5 and its reluctance to undergo facile 1,2 elimination may be attributed to *cis*-orientation of the vicinal hydrogens which in turn suggests that C-6 is substituted with the chlorine atom. The facile oxidation of physalolactone to IV and V, indicating the presence of a 17, 20-glycol system (cf. carbon-carbon bond cleavage of pinacols with chromic acid⁸), settles its gross structure leaving only the stereochemistry to be determined. This structure of physalolactone conforms with the gross structure of the chlorohydrin derivable from 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E (VII)^{9,10}. The CD spectrum of physalolactone indicated *cis*-fusion of rings A and B ($\Delta\epsilon_{339} + 0.11$) and R-configuration at C-22 ($\Delta\epsilon_{239} + 12.35$) as are observed in VII. Conclusive evidence in support of the structure I for physalolactone came from its conversion to 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E (VII) of established structure^{9,10}.

The presence of 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E in this species was reported by Kirson *et al*⁹, who examined the leaves of the plant raised in Israel from the seeds collected from India, and also by the Japanese workers¹⁰. In our case, however, TLC examination of the extract failed to reveal the presence of VII while physalolactone was detected as a major constituent. The possibility of its being an artefact derived from VII could also be ruled out from the fact that the isolation procedure did not involve any contact with HCl or chlorinated solvents. Physalolactone is thus a new addition to the group of naturally occurring chlorine-containing withanolides isolated from the Solanaceae family^{11,12}.

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken with a *Toshniwal* apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer in *nujol*, UV spectra were measured with a Cary 17 instrument using spectral grade methanol. PMR spectra were determined on

HX-90 MHz instrument and chemical shifts are relative to TMS. Mass spectra were recorded on MS-50 instrument. TLC was carried out on chromatoplates on silica gel G (Sarabhai M.) and column chromatography was carried out with silica gel (B.D.H.).

Plant material. The leaves of *Physalis peruviana* Linn. were collected in the month of April from the fields in the suburbs of Varanasi city.

Isolation : Crushed and air-dried leaves of *Physalis peruviana* (2 kg) were exhaustively extracted with ethanol (95%) by cold percolation and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a vol. of ca. 1.5 l, diluted with equal vol. of H₂O and extracted first with petroleum ether (60-80°) to remove fatty matters and pigments and then with ether. The ether extract was washed (H₂O), dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent was removed to leave a green residue (ca. 20 g) which was chromatographed over silica gel (400 g); the column was eluted with benzene-ethyl acetate mixtures. Benzene-ethyl acetate (3:2) eluates yielded physalolactone (2.0 g).

Physalolactone (I) : M.P. 227-28° (MeOH), $[\alpha]_D^{20} +29.4^\circ$ (pyridine; c, 0.2), UV : λ_{max} 217nm (ϵ , 11,700); IR : ν_{max} 3625; 3570, 3350 cm⁻¹ (-OH), 1673 cm⁻¹ (C=O); CD λ_{max} in nm ($\Delta\epsilon$) : 363 (+0.07), 353 (+0.1), 348 (+0.14), 338 (+0.11), 306 (-0.33), 239 (+12.35), 205 (-3.53); MS : m/e 538/540 (M⁺, intensity ratio 3:1), 520/522 (M-H₂O), 502/504 (M-2H₂O), 484/486 (M-3H₂O), 466/468 (M-4H₂O), 448 (M-HCl-3H₂O), 430 (M-HCl-4H₂O), 412 (M-HCl-5H₂O), 395/397 (M-125-H₂O), 379 (M-125-2H₂O), 359/361 (M-125-3H₂O), 281, 223, 170, 169, 153, 152, 126, 125, 38 (H⁸⁷Cl), 36 (H³⁵Cl); (Found : C, 60.28%; H, 7.32%; C₂₈H₃₀O₈Cl. H₂O requires C, 60.38, H, 7.37%).

Acetylation of I : (100-mg) with Ac₂O and Et₃N, overnight at room temp., gave monoacetate (II), m.p. 211-212° (MeOH); ν_{max} 3435, 3200, 1760, 1690 and 1635 cm⁻¹; MS : m/e 580/582 (M⁺), 562/564 (M-H₂O), 544/546 (M-2H₂O), 526/528 (M-3H₂O), 520/522 (M-AcOH), 502/504 (M-AcOH-H₂O), 484/486 (M-AcOH-2H₂O), 466 (M-HCl-AcOH-H₂O), 448 (M-AcOH-HCl-2H₂O), 437/439 (M-125-H₂O), 419/421 (M-125-2H₂O), 169 (base peak), 153, 152, 126, 125, 38 and 36.

MnO₂ oxidation of I to III : A solution of I (200 mg) in dry acetone was stirred with active MnO₂ (1 g) for 48 hr and the reaction mixture was filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and crystallised from MeOH as light yellow needles (140 mg), m.p. 254-55° (dec.); UV : λ_{max} 227 nm; IR : ν_{max} 3525, 3420, 1695 cm⁻¹; MS : m/e 536/538 (M⁺), 518/520, 500/502, 482/484, 464/466, 446, 393/395, 375/377, 357/359, 267, 170, 169, 153, 152, 126, 125, 38, 36.

Jones oxidation of I to IV and V : A stirred solution of I (800 mg) in acetone was titrated with Jones reagent at room temp. The supernatant was separated from chromium salts and evaporated to

dryness. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Benzene-acetone (9:1) eluates gave a homogeneous oil (IV) which gave a crystalline DNP derivative, silky needles, m.p. 198-200° (dec.) (from EtOH-CH₂Cl₂); IR : ν_{max} 3320 (-NH), 1725 (lactone carbonyl) and 1620 cm⁻¹ (-C=N-); PMR (CDCl₃) : δ , 1.93 (3H, s), 2.02 (3H, s), 2.20 (3H, s), 2.47 (1H, dd, J=18 & 5 Hz), 2.87 (1H, dd, J=18 & 11 Hz), 5.06 (1H, dd, J=11 & 5 Hz), 7.91 (1H, d, J=10 Hz), 8.36 (1H, dd, J=10 & 2.5 Hz), 9.11 (1H, d, J=2.5 Hz), 11.10 (1H, s); (Found : C, 51.47, H, 4.71, N, 15.81% M⁺, 348. C₁₅H₁₆N₄O₆ requires C, 51.72, H, 4.59, N, 16.09%, M, 348).

Benzene-acetone (4:1) eluate from the column gave a solid (V) which crystallised from acetone as pale yellow needles, m. p. 284-85° (dec.), UV : λ_{max} 227 (ϵ , 8,700), 375 nm (ϵ , 83), IR : ν_{max} 1750 (cyclopentanone), 1716 (probably due to enone with adjacent electronegative substituent¹³), 1670 (enone), 3515, 3340 cm⁻¹ (-OH); MS : m/e 366/368 (M⁺), 348/350 (M-H₂O), 330 (M-HCl), 312 (M-HCl-H₂O), 294 (M-HCl-2H₂O), 266, 231, 175, 91, 38, 36 (Found : C, 61.97, H, 6.41% C₁₉H₂₂O₅Cl requires C, 62.21, H, 6.27%).

Dehydration of ketone V to VI—A mixture of ketone V (100 mg), Ac₂O (1 ml) and freshly-fused KHSO₄ was refluxed for 10 min¹⁴ and the reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice to decompose acid anhydride and then extracted with CHCl₃. The extract was washed, dried and evaporated to dryness. The residue (65 mg) was chromatographed over Al₂O₃ and eluted with benzene. The eluates showing single spot on thin layer chromatoplate were pooled together and crystallised from methanol as needles, m. p. 244-45° (becomes sticky on keeping), MS : m/e 390/392 (M⁺), 362/364 (M-CO), 355 (M-Cl), 348/350 (M-CH₃CO), 330/332 (M-AcOH), 312 (M-CH₃COCl), 295 (M-HCl-OAc), 294 (M-HCl-AcOH), 267 (M-HCl-OAc-CO), 266 (M-HCl-AcOH-CO), 251 (M-HCl-AcOH-CO-CH₃).

Conversion of I to VII : A mixture of physalolactone (100 mg) and freshly-fused KOAc (100 mg) was refluxed with ethanol for 16 hr, the reaction mixture was diluted with equal vol. of H₂O and extracted with ether. The ether ext. was washed, dried and evaporated to dryness to give a residue which was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) removed unreacted physalolactone and with ethyl acetate afforded 4 β -hydroxywithanolide B (40 mg), $[\alpha]_D^{20} +112.3^\circ$ (Pyridine). It was identified by co-TLC with authentic sample¹⁰ with which it showed superimposable IR spectrum. (Found : C, 66.76; H, 7.68%; C₂₈H₃₀O₈ requires C, 66.93; H, 7.57%).

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